

INFLUENCE OF AUTOMATION CHANGES ON GO-AROUND OPERATIONS: A DATA-DRIVEN APPROACH

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Abstract: *A variety of causes led air traffic controllers (ATCOs) to instruct go-around procedures. The most frequent are non-stabilized approach, loss of separation or insufficient separation between aircraft, so that speed monitoring or separations in approaches are particularly significant for an improvement in operational safety. Nowadays, ATCOs use the speed parameter provided by their Controller Working Position (CWP) to apply relevant restrictions to aircraft within their responsibility. This parameter is obtained from the radar tracks and it can differ from the actual speed of the aircraft. The objective of this research was to select appropriate factors influencing go-around procedures and compare them before and after the introduction of the speed parameter on the CWP display at Barcelona airport.*

Keywords: *air traffic control, airport, safety, go-around*

1. INTRODUCTION

Some of the main causes affecting airport safety are the go-around procedures or the losses of separations (LoS) between consecutive aircraft in approach and landing. The statistics show that among worldwide fatal accidents between 2011 and 2020, 54% occurred during the final approach or in the landing phase [1]. According to accident analyses, the go-around procedures are often improperly executed because of their complexity and high tempo stress [2]. A go-around maybe initiated by the pilot or the air traffic controller (ATCO) representing a decision not to continue an approach, or not to continue a landing, following procedures to conduct another approach or to divert to another airport [3]. Go-around can happen at any point from the final approach fix to the touchdown due to conditions such as wind shear, runway incursion or unstabilized approach [3]. However, go-round procedure usually occurs at low altitude and low speed, close to the ground, which makes these operations difficult to perform properly. In these situations, the ATCOs have a key role in ensuring the safe and efficient go-around operations. In fact, the ATCOs have to deal with continuously congested airspace with a high level of alertness in order to maintain the safety and efficiency of air traffic operations [4]. On the other hand, the close and timely precise cooperation between pilots and ATCOs is crucial to maintain safety of the approach/landing phase. To make that possible, better support of ATCOs decision making and instructions to aircrew relating to landing approaches is required.

The purpose of the research presented in this paper is to analyse the factors that contribute to go-around occurrences i.e. how they change with introduction of new information/label to the Controller Working Position (CWP). The idea is to analyse operational data in respect to the introduction of the specific information: indicated airspeed (IAS) or Mach number, in the flight label on the radar screen on CWP so that ATCO will have it at his/her disposal and will be able to apply new speed restrictions between pairs of approaching aircraft to maintain safe separation. The analysis is performed before and after the change on tower ATCOs CWP at Barcelona airport using the operational data in 2017 (before change introduction) and 2019 (after change introduction).

The aircraft speed in the final approach is a valuable well-known safety term. Currently, the label of a flight that appears on the CWP (Figure 1-left), shows the horizontal speed term, obtained from the radar track, but does not have to match with the current aircraft speed or IAS. However, the proposal is to add one more term, in the fourth row of the label, showing the IAS or Mach number. Being a known parameter on the aircraft, to be displayed in real time on CWP, it will be sent from the aircraft system as DAP (Downlinked Aircraft Parameters). A similar structure to the horizontal speed is proposed (Figure 1-middle), in dozens of knots with the indication “I” to understand that it is the IAS.

Depending on the flight level, the speed data presented in CWP will be indicated in Mach number or knots (IAS) (Figure 1-right picture). Therefore, if that speed data is not available, the tactical constraints will remain the same, so there will be no impact on the current Human Machine Interface. This change is expected to reduce the number of go-around by non-stabilized approaches or by LoS, among others, as the ATCO will be able to safely separate aircraft based on its IAS. Indirectly and due to the restrictions imposed by the ATCO, these speed changes will affect the pilots that they will have to modify according to the ATCO instructions.

Figure 1: Current (left), proposed (middle) flight label and flight label showing MACH on CWP (right)

The paper consists of four sections. The introduction and problem definition is presented in Section 1, as well as the purpose of this paper. In Section 2, five step methodology is presented, followed by the results obtained in each step in Section 3. Section 4 is the conclusion of the paper.

2. METHODOLOGY

In order to assess benefits due to introduction of the IAS label on CWP two scenarios are compared – before and after implementation of this change. Recorded operational data for two summer months (June and July) in year 2017 are used to represent before the change scenario. Same months in year 2019 are used to represent for after the change case. The first benefits of this change were expected in 2020, two years after its introduction. But due to COVID-19 pandemic impact on air traffic, year 2020 could not be used as a reference. Two sub-scenarios were planned, corresponding to nominal weather conditions and conditions with severe weather activity (with increased number of go-around).

The analysis is conducted through several steps as following:

- Step I – selection of the sample days for the analysis before and after the change;
- Step II – analysis of runway configuration schemes and available runway throughput;
- Step III – analysis of weather conditions;
- Step IV – extraction of the selected indicators and before and after-change scenario comparison;
- Step V – analysis of other possible contributors to go-around operation.

3. RESULTS

3.1. Step I –sample days

First step was to select the sample days with high traffic occupancy in summer period of 2017 and 2019. The daily number of arrivals for all sample days in both years was required in order to extract days with high occupancy.

The sample is composed by 119 complete days (61 in 2017 and 58 in 2019). To select the high-occupancy days the maximum Arrival Sequencing and Metering Area (ASMA) congestion was computed for each day, and then the days with the highest values were selected. This approach was adopted with the idea to focus more on highest congestion and how it is managed. In the Figure 2, the three dashed lines represent three possible thresholds for selection.

For further analysis the second threshold is adopted. The selected sample includes: 41 days in 2017 (June: 19 days and July: 22 days), and 48 days in 2019 (June: 24 days and July: 24 days).

Figure 2: The sample days extraction (left) and number of weekdays in the sample (right) for 2017 and 2019

3.2. Step II – runway configuration and runway throughput

In case of Barcelona airport [5] there are three runway configurations in use during the day: West configuration, parallel runways (25L and 25R, default configuration: 07-23h), East configuration, parallel runways (07L and 07R), and North configuration, intersecting runways (07R and 02, mostly active during the night). In each configurations runways are used in segregated mode, one for arrivals and one for departures. In Figure 3 and Figure 4 comparison between planned runway configuration and actual runway configurations during the day is presented. Alternative configuration, East, is used up to 30% of time (with exception of one hour in 2017, when it was 70% of time in use). Apart from three basic configurations, West Aln configuration also appears as alternative configuration during the night time.

Figure 3: Daily distribution of Planned and Actual Runway configuration, selected days in summer 2017

Figure 4: Daily distribution of Planned and Actual Runway configuration, selected days in summer 2019

3.3. Step III – weather

Due to data observed from METAR reports, prevailing weather conditions are relatively mild, and due to that could not be directly connected to go-around operations. Cross-winds and tail-winds are analysed for each go-around operation separately (in step V). Wind direction and speed on altitudes/heights within final approach, as well as appearance of wind shear could be contributing factors, but those data were not available.

3.4. Step IV – key indicators

The number of go-around operations are proposed as a key indicator for tracking potential benefits of the change. The separation between aircraft pairs on final approach and wake turbulence category for each aircraft were extracted from the data as well as separation distribution before and after the change. Possible separation violations were also addressed.

The total number of arrivals for the selected days was 21.214 and 25.761 operations in 2017 and 2019, respectively. Within selected days in a traffic sample the percentage of go-around operations in relation to total number of arrivals was 0,27% (0,31% and 0,23% of number of arrivals in June and July, respectively) for 2017, and 0,35% (0,32% and 0,38% of number of arrivals in June and July, respectively) for 2019.

Share of go-around operations in a total number of arrivals is very low, as expected. The distribution of go-arounds per days of week is shown in Figure 5 (left). In 2017 the highest percentage of go-arounds occurred on Monday, and in 2019 on Thursday and Sunday. In 2017 the highest share of go-around operations occurred in evening (17th and 21st hours - 12,07% of go-arounds), while in 2019 the highest share of go-around operations was in the morning (8th hour - 15,38% of go-arounds) (Figure 5, right).

Figure 5: Go-around operations per days (left), and hourly distribution of go-around (right) in 2017 and 2019

In Figure 6, the hourly distribution of go-around is merged with the average hourly distribution of arrivals for 2017 and 2019 respectively. It seems (without entering into correlation analysis) that a higher number of arrivals are followed by higher number of go-around in both years.

According to wake turbulence categorization, in 2017, there were 86.21% go-around operations performed by medium aircraft lead by medium aircraft (M-M aircraft pair, the follower performing go-around). The number of go-around operations between other pairs of aircraft is much smaller. As in 2017, the vast majority of realized go-around operations in 2019 were associated to M-M aircraft type pair (75.82% of go-around operations).

Figure 6: Average number of arrivals and go-around hourly distribution, in 2017 and 2019

Separation distribution for M-M aircraft pairs is presented in Figure 7 for sample days in 2017 and 2019. Comparing the two cases, it can be seen that the separation minima are met, but that the average separation for the case of M-M aircraft category is slightly lower in 2019 (5.83 NM in 2019 vs. 5.99 NM in 2017), which can be interpreted as slight improvement of the system performance due to IAS introduction in the CWPs flight label. For other aircraft pairs, though, the separation was higher in 2019 than in 2017.

The M-M aircraft pairs are observed separately, since that combination of aircraft is the most frequent when it comes to go-around cases. Theoretical distribution best fitting the empirical one is given in Figure 8. Mean separation is 5.82 NM in 2017 and 5.74 NM in 2019. Median also moves towards lower value for 5.0 NM in 2017, to 4.88 NM in 2019.

Ground separation violations were not assessed, since the data required to perform this analysis were not available in the data-base (runway occupancy time, runway incursion events, etc.).

Figure 7: Separation distribution for all aircraft pairs (go-around cases) in 2017 and 2019

Figure 8: Theoretical distribution of M-M aircraft pair's separation, in 2017 and 2019

3.5. Step V – other indicators

In this step, selected factors possibly contributing to go-around were analysed, aiming to explain increased number of go-arounds in 2019 compared to 2017. This analysis includes possible connection of go-around operations to airlines or aircraft types, to runway configuration in use, or other detected anomalies. Go-around operations at Barcelona Airport are mostly performed by low cost airlines that may be a consequence of different descending profiles that include fuel conservation. Low cost airlines mostly fly uniform fleets that consists predominantly of A320 family or B737-700, -800 and MAX aircraft, and these aircraft types take the major shares in go-around operations. A320 aircraft performed 55% of go-arounds in 2017 and 38% in 2019, followed by B737-800 aircraft with 22% (2017) and 19% (2019) share in all go-arounds.

One possible reason for go-around may be postponed ATCO decision for the runway configuration change, allowing operations with stronger tailwind component than commonly accepted 5kt. From Figure 3 and Figure 4, it can be seen that alternative configuration (East) is in use approximately 30% of the time, with one exception in 2017, when it was in use 70% of time between 16h and 17h. This may indicate unfavorable wind conditions during this hour, or one hour before. However, the data does not confirm connection between go-around operations and runway configuration change decisions in these periods. During 16h to 17h hour period there were 10.3% go-arounds (7% when West was active + 3.3% when East was active) in 2017, and only 2.2% in 2019 (all when West was active). All go-arounds in 2017 were performed with headwind or tailwind below 1kt. During previous hour, 15h to 16h, there were only 3.4% go-arounds in 2017 (1.7% when West was active + 1.7% when East was active), but even 13.2% in 2019 (11% when West was active + 2.2% when East was active). This could indicate that in 2019 ATCOs allowed somewhat stronger tailwind to keep West configuration in use, which could have resulted in increase of go-around operations between 15h and 16h. The data do not confirm this, as in 2019 all go around operations in this period were performed with headwind.

Only 8.6% go-around cases possibly occurred due to tailwind (greater than 5kt) in 2017, and only 2.2% cases in 2019 (Figure 9), while there were only 1.7% cases in 2017 and 3.3% cases in 2019 with crosswind above the most restrictive 10kt crosswind limit (for aircraft with reference field length up to 1200m (Figure 10)).

Figure 9: Head/tailwind component for go around cases in 2017 and 2019

Figure 10: Crosswind component for go around cases in 2017 and 2019

4. CONCLUSION

The go-arounds are the most safety-critical operations, so it is necessary to perform them in the safest possible manner. Therefore, the speed of aircraft in the final approach is a valuable well-known safety term. IAS incorporation in the flight label for the CWP is expected to reduce the number of go-arounds by non-stabilized approaches or by LoS, among others.

Based on the performed analysis, benefits caused by introduction of IAS speed label on the screen of CWP, were not confirmed using the number of go-arounds. Number of go-arounds increased in 2019 (after change), compared to same period in 2017 (before change). However, the relative number of go-around operations does not increase from 2017 to 2019, meaning that the current safety level is kept despite an increased demand pressure. Other benefits of the change could be associated to indicators that cannot be extracted directly from the traffic data, like decreased ATCO workload, leading to increased throughput in the future.

The main benefits of IAS introduction were expected to be observed in Summer 2020 (after two years since introduction), but due to the COVID-19 impact, only 1.5 years data after the change (including Summer 2019 and half of the Summer 2018) were available. So, the analysis should be repeated when the air traffic stabilizes. Accordingly, the further research should take into account some indicators and data related to them that were not analyzed in the current research due to the lack of available information (i.e. runway occupancy time and runway incursions by another aircraft).

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